

SOME SPECIES OF THE SPECIES TARAXACUM L. BIOECOLOGY AND PHARMACEUTICAL PROPERTIES

Jamoldinova Gulnoza

2 nd year student of the Faculty of Biology, Andijan State University

Ergasheva Gulmira Ostonovna

Doctoral student (PhD) of Andijan State University

gergasheva085@gmail.com

Abstract: In this article, *Taraxacum officinale* L. species distributed in Andijan city. Botanical description, distribution areas, taxonomy and medicinal properties of *Ceratophorum*, *taraxacum officinale* sups weredescribed based on various literature.

Key words: allergic level, taxon, family, phenology.

Taraxacum officinale, dandelion or common dandelion is a perennial flowering plant belonging to the Asteraceae family. The common dandelion is famous for its yellow flower heads, which turn into round balls of many silvery fruits that disperse in the wind. The common dandelion grows in moist soil areas in temperate regions of the world. They are very flexible plants, able to grow in different environments, resistant to extreme temperatures and low humidity. As a result of this resilience, in addition to rapid reproduction, dandelions are widely distributed due to human activities. Its homeland is Eurasia, but it is also found in the Americas and southern Africa. It is often considered a weed, especially in lawns and roadsides, but the leaves, flowers, and roots are sometimes used in herbal medicine and as food.

Taraxacum officinale - usually grows from unbranched branches and produces several hollow, leafless flower stems. It is usually 5–40 cm high, but sometimes it is up to 70 cm. The stems are purple in color, erect or drooping, and form flower heads that are as tall or taller than the leaves. The leaves grow vertically or spread horizontally. The leaves have wingless or narrowly winged leaves. The stem may be bare or sparsely covered with short hairs. The plants have a milky latex and the

leaves are all basal. The yellow flower heads have no bracts and all the so-called flowers are ligulate and bisexual. In most genera, fruits are produced mainly by apomixis. The leaves are 5–45 cm long and 1–10 cm long, oblong or oval in shape, and the base gradually narrows to the bottom. The edges of the leaves are usually shallowly lobed [1].

Carl Linnaeus named *Leontodon officinale* in 1753. The current species name *Taraxacum* may be derived from the Arabic *Tharakhchakon* or the Greek *Tarraxos*. The specific name *officinale* refers to its value as a medicinal herb and is derived from the word *opificina*, which later means *officina*, workshop or pharmacy. It contains fossils from the glacial and interglacial periods in Europe.

Plants originally introduced to North America as food are triploid and reproduce primarily by obligate gametophytic apomixis. Although sexual dandelion plants are known in North America, almost all are clones that produce genetically identical seeds through apomixis. There are three known subspecies of *Taraxacum officinale*, including:

Taraxacum officinale is commonly called common dandelion, fleshy dandelion, horned dandelion, or rough dandelion. Its native Canada and the western United States are listed in some sources as *Taraxacum ceratophorum*. *Taraxacum officinale* subsp. *vulgare* Schinz R. Keller, commonly called common dandelion. Alaska is the homeland of two of them, where they grow and develop. *Taraxacum officinale* L. (dandelion) is a weed in Europe, with diploid sexual populations in southern regions and partially overlapping populations of diploid sexual and triploid or tetraploid apomictes in central and northern regions. These European dandelions can be divided into two groups. The first group, like most seed plants, reproduces sexually. This group consists of dandelions that have a diploid set of chromosomes and are sexually incompatible. Sexual reproduction involves the reduction of the number of somatic chromosomes by meiosis, followed by the restoration of the number of somatic chromosomes by fertilization. Diploid dandelions have eight pairs of chromosomes, and normal pairing of homologous chromosomes occurs during metaphase I of meiosis. The second group includes polyploid (mainly triploid) apomictes, functional

endosperm is also formed without prior fertilization. In contrast to sexual diploids, in triploid apomictes, the pairing of chromosomes is strongly reduced in metaphase I. However, pairing is still sufficient to allow some recombination between homologous chromosomes [2].

Taraxacum officinale is native to Europe and Asia and was originally brought to the Americas as a food crop. It is now naturalized in North America, South Africa, South America, New Zealand, Australia and India. It is found in all 50 US states and most Canadian provinces. Plant. in temperate regions of the world, it grows in lawns, roadsides, disturbed banks, waterways and other places with moist soil. In areas where the plant is more difficult to grow, such as the tropics, it is often experimented by collectors in areas where people import seeds from abroad. Some books describe it as a noxious weed and a nuisance in residential and recreational areas in North America. It is also an important weed in agriculture and causes great economic losses due to its infestation in many crops worldwide [4].

Taraxacum officinale can serve as an indicator plant for potassium and calcium in the soil, as the plant grows well in soils with relatively low concentrations of calcium. (Figure 1)

Overview of *Taraxacum officinale*

Dandelion is a common colonizer of disturbed habitats, both from wind-blown seeds and from seed germination. Seeds remain viable for many years, with research showing germination after nine years. This species is a prolific seed producer, producing 54 to 172 seeds per head, and a single plant can produce over 5,000 seeds per year. According to data, more than 97,000,000 seeds per hectare can be produced

by dense stands of dandelions [5]. Its seeds are spread by the wind up to several hundred meters from the growing area. A common contaminant in seeds as well as crop and forage seeds is a driver. The plants can adapt to different soils and cold temperatures for seed germination, but they should be in the top 2.5 cm of soil. Dandelion can also regenerate itself from root pieces.

Its leaves, stems, flowers, and roots contain nutrients such as vitamins A and C, as well as calcium and iron, and are nutritious when consumed. Dandelions are found on six continents and have been collected for food since prehistoric times, but commercially cultivated varieties for consumption are mainly distributed in Eurasia and North America. To make the leaves more palatable, they are often blanched to remove the bitterness or eaten in the same way as spinach. Dandelion greens have been part of traditional Kashmiri cuisine, Lebanese cuisine, Spanish cuisine, Italian cuisine, Albanian cuisine, Slovenian, Sephardic Jewish Chinese, Greek cuisine, and Korean cuisine. In Crete, the leaves of the varieties called "Mari" (Li), "Mariaki" or "Koproradiko" (Koproradiko) are eaten raw or boiled by the locals. *T. megalorhizon*, a species endemic to Crete, is consumed in the same way; it is found only at high altitudes (1000–1600 meters) and in autumn fields and is called *pentaramia* (*pinarama*) or *agrioradico* (*agriordi*). Flower petals, along with other products, are usually used to make citrus fruits, dandelion wine. Its crushed, roasted roots can be used as a decaffeinated coffee alternative. Dandelion is also commonly used to make the traditional English soft drink Dandelion and Burdock, and is an ingredient in root beer. Dandelions were once considered a delicacy by Victorian gentlemen, who used them mainly in salads and sandwiches [3].

Allergy. Eating dandelions or their pollen can cause an allergic reaction in humans, but the risk is mild. Latex containing sesquiterpene lactones is found in high concentrations in the main root and stems of common dandelion. However, only a few researchers provide data on the risk of mild allergic dermatitis for people with lactone hypersensitivity [5].

In conclusion, it can be said that the biomorphology, ecology and medicinal properties of *Taraxacum officinale* have been well studied, and no scientific

researches have been conducted in Uzbekistan on the morphology of the pollen of this plant and their levels of allergic effects. Based on the literature of foreign countries, it was found that the allergic level corresponds to 2.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Milliy Ensiklopediyasi (2000-2005)
2. Jurgenson P.B., Kaplanov L.G., “Ekologiya masalalari” 1935-yil 35-bet
3. Baeva V.M., “O'simlikshunoslik asoslari” 2004-yil 115-116 bet
4. Xavf ostidagi turlar. Qizil kitobi 2013-yil
5. O'. Prator, X.M.Xudoyberganov., “Botanika darsliklarida qo'llaniladigan yuksak o'simliklar sistematikasiga oid kategoriya va taksonlar” Qo'llanma. Toshkent- 2004